

ACADEMIC EXCELLENCE THROUGH MULTI-SENSORY APPROACH: A MODEL FOR CLASSROOM TEACHING

Gururaj Ganapati Gouda 1*, Laveena D'Mello 2**

1*Research Scholar, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India.

Email: gururajitgi@gmail.com

2**Assistant Professor, Social Work Department, Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Mangalore, Karnataka, India. Email: [lavynoronha@gmail.com](mailto:lavyronha@gmail.com)

Abstract

Our senses are natural gifts which transfer information to the thinking brain to understand what is being presented to us in the form of sight, hearing, touch, smell, taste. These senses determine to some extent how we understand the concept being presented and recall instructional contents or information. To this effect, teachers at all levels of educational sector keep these in mind and endeavour to apply the Multi-Sensory Approach in presenting their instructional contents in a classroom situation to take care of the uniqueness of the individual learners and bring the best academic excellence. A Multi-sensory approach is an effective model named "Itagi's Model of Multi-Sensory Approach" developed by Gururaj Itagi. Highlighting various methods, strategies and techniques in teaching process focussing on individual learning style to maximize student's academic excellence. This model is framed based on the different learning style of students. This framework considers integrated phases of teaching such as auditory, visual and kinaesthetic approach. The model focuses on Adolescence (aged 12-18 years) mainly on students with scholastic backwardness.

Keywords: Academic Excellence, Multi-Sensory Approach, Classroom Teaching, Students & Teachers.

1. INTRODUCTION:

A classroom is a place in an educational institution where teaching and learning carried out. Teachers and students engage themselves in the school for academic interaction. The classroom must be equipped with necessary materials which could support quality teaching and best learning. The new Education Policy-2019 which is prepared by Dr. Kasthuri Rangan committee and asked for public opinion recognises, from information received by teachers, students, educational scientists, and educators of different sectors, that the present curriculum content is currently overloaded [1]. Finally, students are most of the time removed from the social support of teachers and are expected to compete rather than cooperate with each other in reading [2]. The modern meaning of "learning style" indicates a much broader look at how a student responds to the learning situations and how a student functions as a learner [3] [4]. School fear (School Phobia) among children is affecting the academic performance of the children and their day today's activities. This is also one of the major reason for children's school dropout. It is highly recommended to expertize the teachers to have an insight into

phobic disorders and their impacts on children [5]. The children with several behavioural problems in the school are not given importance to understand the real cause behind their problems [6].

Need of Student Centred Classroom Teaching for Academic Excellence: Different Committees set up by MHRD proposed “Learning Without Burden” and highlighted the sever need for reducing and revising our overcrowded curriculum content load in favour of a more engaging, holistic, experiential, and analysis-based form of learning [1]. Academic excellence refers to the increased level of learning interest, active participation in teaching and learning process, experiential learning based on individual learning style and Maximized performance in learning and examination [6].

2. OBJECTIVES:

The below objectives are set up with the aim of identifying strengths and weakness of present teaching methodology and explore the effective teaching approach which is mainly focused on the different learning styles of learning individuals in the classroom. The objectives of this study is to understand the different goals of Multi-Sensory Approach Model, to explore the experiential learning through Multi-Sensory Approach Model, to develop the student centred classroom teaching through Multi-Sensory Approach model, and to understand the different benefits from the use of Multi-Sensory Approach model.

3. GOALS OF MULTI-SENSORY APPROACH:

This particular study also focussing on the classroom approach aiming to teach the individual’s learning needs based on their learning style such as auditory, visual and kinaesthetic learning [7]. The major goals of Multi-sensory approach are as follows.

Visual Learners: Visual means sight. Every human being is unique in learning, some learners are more active and enjoy learning using their eyes and remember information. Visualized teaching in the classroom was found to significantly increase student learning. The Multi-Sensory Approach is aiming to include teaching strategies which suites to the visual learners and prefers visualization of the subject in classroom teaching [8].

Auditory Learners: Auditory learning refers to learning through sound. Individuals under this category are those who use their ears more to learn and remember information presented to them. They are more sensitised through sound and they enjoy listening. The approach describes a possible way of effective teaching in the classroom considering auditory learners to maximize their academic performance as well as their learning interest [9].

Kinaesthetic Learners: In the teaching and learning situation, some of the learners learn and recall information more effectively using their feelings and involving in the learning activities. These types of learners are physically-oriented individuals. So the aim of the multi-sensory approach is to fulfil the gap in encouraging the students with kinaesthetic learning style in teaching-learning process at the classroom and enhance their understanding ability to maximize their academic performance [10].

So considering learner’s learning capacity the Multi-Sensory Approach brings a new strategic model which helps the teachers to reach every individual in the classroom with different learning style and maximize their active participation in teaching and learning process, increase their academic performance [10].

4. EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING THROUGH MULTI-SENSORY APPROACH:

Experiential learning exists when a personally responsible participant cognitively, effectively, and behaviourally processes knowledge, skills, and attitudes in a learning situation characterized by a high level of active involvement (Hoover and Whitehead 1975).

Child-centered ideas in the classroom have to be planned in teacher-training programs and school with the intention of creating more child-friendly, democratic learning environments and teaching based on student's learning demands focusing on their learning style may enhance better academic output [11].

Figure-1: Human learn through sensory organs

Information obtained through senses such as hearing, seeing, touching, tasting, and smelling all contribute to the way in which people experience their external world. When an individual witness a situation he receive information through his multi-sensory organs. When an Individual see something happening, hear the sound produced and physically involve in the same situation will have a better understanding of what he saw, heard and involved. The message received on any one situation, through multi-sensory organs will enhance the long term memory. It has a quality of personal involvement and being present in the learning event [12] [13].

Multi-Sensory Approach model outlines the manner in which learners gain knowledge and understanding through experiences [14]. Students should have frequent and multiple opportunities to read, write, listen, see, speak and involve in the teaching and learning process. Lesson activities can be modified more appropriately to meet the student's learning needs and abilities. A multi-sensory approach is not only offering participants to have structured experiences but also a reflection upon these experiences in order to learn from them, to link them to their own lives and to experiment with this new knowledge in the following activities and in their daily life which also contains long term memory [15]. Due to inappropriate teaching approach of the teachers in the classroom, many students just don't value their education. The Multi-Sensory Approach in classroom teaching focuses on the learning demands of the students and encourages the students to have experiential learning in the classroom [16].

5. DEVELOPING A STUDENT- CENTRED CLASSROOM TEACHING THROUGH MULTI-SENSORY APPROACH:

Most teachers and students at all levels of education have gone without fully understanding and using their potentials and unique nature as intelligent and creative individuals. Most people have not realised these unique qualities of the individual which made us use a single method of teaching and learning, considering human beings are the same and ignoring the unique nature of man. This might be a reason why most of our academic strategies are ineffective. A combined method that will sensitise most of the sense organs in individual learner becomes an ideal strategy to achieve effective teaching and learning in the classroom [17].

Classroom teaching based on student’s learning style thrives on several benefits. First, the teacher does not hold all of the power to control were students feel helpless. Instead, students share responsibilities and understand their capabilities as learners. Second, students are motivated to think critically and question the presented material. Third, teachers are also learners and they seek to be taught as much as possible, themselves, may teach. Fourth, students have insight and control of their learning. Which even helps the teachers to get reduced burden of working with scholastic backward students. Teaching and learning effort to be conducted in a more interactive manner, questions will be encouraged, and classroom teaching will contain more creative, collaborative, and exploratory activities for students for deeper and more experiential learning [18] [19].

Figure-2: Multi-Sensory Approach Model

Approach for Auditory Learners: Auditory learner depends on remembering information taught through sounds. Who is doing the speaking is not a matter for the auditory learner, it may be a recording, and Teacher's talk or even himself reading. Auditory learners naturally focus on sound patterns, they benefit more when classroom teaching happens by using sound patterns rather than the written patterns. Because these type of learners depend more on their auditory memory. It is a responsibility of teachers that they adopt an effective teaching method as explained below [20].

- (a) **Talk:** the teacher in the classroom teaching should be well trained in effective communication and be capable to pronounce the words fluently and melodiously. So that the students who are auditory learners enjoy their teaching and have a better understanding of the concept taught in the classroom.
- (b) **Audio Aids:** In the process of teaching teachers can also use different audio gadgets such as speakers, audio player, and mike etc. teachers can record teaching and help the students who would like to listen to it whenever they want. Teachers also can play melodious background music which when they have a session in the classroom.
- (c) **Musical Instruments:** Using different musical instruments to play the music in the classroom will influence the auditory learners towards paying attention and active involvement in the teaching and learning process.
- (d) **Question and Answer Method:** Students must be encouraged and given the opportunity to ask the questions and give answers. If the teachers make their session as most interactive one students will defiantly have to enjoy learning and improve their academic performance.
- (e) **Group Discussion:** Even auditory learners enjoy having more discussion in the learning and teaching process. Teachers must encourage the students to have interaction between teachers and students and students and students. Teachers also can divide students into multiple groups and encourage them for group discussion.

Approach for Kinaesthetic Learners: The kinaesthetic learners engage themselves in debating, discussion, role-playing, demonstration, and many other learning activities for the concepts they are learning in the classroom to understand and retain as long term memory. Careful planning by the teacher in classroom teaching with kinaesthetic learners will enhance student's capacity in learning and maximize their academic performance because kinaesthetic learners acquire information by sharing and cooperating with teacher and peers [21] [3].

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- (a) **Read and Write Practice:** Teachers can encourage students with a kinaesthetic learning style to have repetitive reading and writing practice. So that students will get engaged both physically and mentally in the teaching and learning process.
 - (b) **Activities:** Different activities planned by the teachers in classroom teaching also will encourage the students to get physically involved in the learning process. Roleplay, Drama, Indoor and Outdoor activities, research projects, experiments etc are the best methods to influence the students with kinaesthetic learning style towards better learning.
 - (c) **Practical:** Use of laboratories, indoor and outdoor experiments, demonstration related to the lesson will help the kinaesthetic learners to enjoy learning and have increased understanding.
 - (d) **Group Discussion:** Students with a kinaesthetic learning style must be encouraged for the group discussion so that they actively involved in clarifying doubts and sharing information.

Approach for Visual Learners: Visual learners enjoy receiving information through their eyes. Visualization of lessons in classroom teaching will enhance visual learner's active participation in the teaching and learning process. Displaying videos, writing on white or blackboard, effective use of the digital board, teacher's body language etc are the effective methods through which visual learners enjoy learning and increase their academic performance [22].

- (a) **Body Language:** Body language is one of the effective methods for effective communication. Visual learners understand better when teachers use body language along with classroom teaching. Facial expressions, body movements and actions will effectively pass the messages to the learners. But most of the teachers in Indian schools even don't move from one place when they are in classroom teaching.
- (b) **Demonstration:** Teachers can convert any lessons into the demonstration. Using a few students or he or she can put themselves to present the demonstration on any decided concept. More than orally explaining the lessons converting them in a visualized method of demonstration is better for visual learners to have an effective understanding and maximized academic performance.
- (c) **Video Aids:** Different technologies such as Digital boards, TV, Video projectors etc can be used effectively in classroom teaching so that the visual learners can experience and have improved understanding of the lessons taught in the class. Teachers can plan their subject teaching as a visualized method of teaching using power point presentation, Sowing related videos, short films, animated videos which even influence more for the visual learners for better learning.
- (d) **Material Display:** In the process of teaching, the teacher can display any materials or things related to the lesson. For example, a teacher would like to teach about triangles or any others shapes so she can use a triangle made in wood or any other materials to the students so that the visual learners have visualized learning about the triangle.
- (e) **Use of White and Black Board:** Every classroom has a chalkboard that may be blackboard or whiteboard, these boards must be used effectively. Teachers must use the boards for writing the concept planned to teach. Drawing, writing title, an important point, mind map, calculation, tables, map or any other diagrams are the effective methods presenting on board to teach visual learners effectively.

6. BENEFITS OF MULTI-SENSORY APPROACH:

Poor teaching in the classroom has a more direct impact on the reading performance of children [23]. Multi-Sensory Approach has the capacity to help the student with different learning style to have an efficient and effective understanding and realisation of the importance of teaching-learning objectives. Therefore, the individual's brain has evolved to develop, learn and operate optimally in multisensory environments [24]. Organizing teaching-learning activities in the classroom that helps the teaching in making the total unit of learners quite clear to their learning ability. It will also help students in acquiring all the learning experiences widely through effective involvement and cooperative learning [18].

Students gather sensory stimuli for three modalities such as vision, touch and audition that seem to fit best with the desired learning. This helps the learners to develop ideas about the different ways in which an experience can be acquired on the subject taught in the classroom [12]. The Multi-Sensory Approach Model makes its primary focus on engaging students in a process that best enhances their learning capacity. Learning will be conceived as a continuing reconstruction of learning experience [25]. We are living in a multi-sensory environment. The brain also involved to learn and operate in classroom environments in which an integrated model of Multi-Sensory Approach is been carried out. However, Multi-Sensory-Approach strategies can better approximate natural settings of teaching and are more effective for learning [26].

Figure-3: Memory Benefits from the Multi-Sensory Approach [27].

Students learn more when the content of teaching is presented in their best modality seems to be supported by classroom experiences, and offers the hope of maximizing each child's learning by planning different lessons and generalizing them for each type of learner. It also increases student's understanding of necessary skills, a variety of media and methods are incorporated while presenting the lesson in the classroom teaching [10]. The utilization of the Senses of Sight, Speech, hearing and touch of the individual in order to learn will enhance their learning ability and maximises there learning interest. This model is also helpful for children, as well as those with learning disabilities, children learn more effectively using their multi senses [1]. When students were taught with Multi-Sensory Approach resources, (although initially through their most preferred learning modality), increased performance in academic as well as active participation in the learning process can be seen. This is a powerful tool for reinforcing our classroom teaching in three important ways. First, it helps get the information across through multi senses. Second, it helps the students to process the

information received. And, third, it helps students more freely reclaim information already learned from teachers. Using a variety of senses simply opens up more doorways into the brain [28] [3]. There are no spirits than the motivation to influence an individual towards achieving their learning goals. The greatest achievers always lay down behind the inspiration of one or another person's, situations or by the stories of success. Motivation is an important aspect behind life leaving of each mankind. The presented model plays a major role in the creation of great hope and motivation among students in classroom learning [29] [30].

8. CONCLUSION:

Our senses are natural gifts which transfer information to the thinking brain to understand what is being presented to us in the form of sight, hearing, touch, smell, taste. These senses determine to some extent how we understand the concept being presented and recall instructional contents or information. To this effect, teachers at all levels of educational sector keep these in mind and endeavour to apply the Multi-Sensory Approach in presenting their instructional contents in a classroom situation to take care of the uniqueness of the individual learners and bring the best academic excellence [31]. This model must be adopted as a value addition to the formal education system of the country to build effective teaching and experiential learning in the classroom for maximizing the academic excellence of the students.

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